

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE AND MACHINE LEARNING ALGORITHMS IN DETERMINING A PERSON'S SOLVENCY

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Abstract. *This study provides information on decision-making in determining the solvency of an individual, which has become a topical issue today. It is devoted to research on the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms in determining the solvency of individuals. The study analyzes intelligent systems and technologies used by financial institutions, credit bureaus, and insurance companies to automate decision-making processes, increase accuracy, and minimize financial risks. The study discusses the characteristics, advantages, and limitations of credit scoring systems such as FICO Score and VantageScore, banks' internal models, as well as modern machine learning algorithms such as Gradient Boosting (XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost), Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines, and neural networks. A combined approach (traditional scoring systems and artificial intelligence, machine learning algorithms) is highlighted as the most effective strategy for ensuring financial stability and optimizing decision-making processes. In the future, the integration of innovative technologies such as artificial intelligence, machine learning, and blockchain is expected to provide more sustainable and effective solutions for the financial sector.*

Keywords: *income, Artificial intelligence, Credit history, Determining a person's solvency, Data analysis, Financial risk management, FICO Score, Machine learning, VantageScore.*

I. Introduction.

In the current era, the digital economy and a number of related effective technologies, including e-commerce and e-business, are rapidly entering our lives. Determining a person's solvency is considered one of the most important tools for financial institutions, credit bureaus and insurance companies today. In making these decisions, in order to increase the accuracy and reduce the number of errors, intelligent algorithmic technologies are widely used. For example, in order to create conditions for the rapid development of modern information technologies in order to implement the digital economy in the state administration system in our republic, as well as to ensure information security, the Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ - 3832 dated 03.07.2018 "On measures to develop the digital economy and the sphere of crypto-asset circulation in the Republic of Uzbekistan" can also be included in the list of such measures. According to this resolution, the following steps are taken to further develop the digital economy in Uzbekistan. The most important developmental tasks are:

It is based on the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the Law "Formation of credit history and the correctness of credit information" and relevant decisions of the Central Bank. These laws determine the scope of collection, processing and use of personal financial

information. In accordance with this legislation, financial institutions are required to analyze the credit history of applicants and determine their ability to pay. This study is devoted to the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms in determining the solvency of individuals, their effectiveness and limitations. Traditional credit scoring systems (FICO Score, VantageScore), internal models of banks, and modern machine learning algorithms such as Gradient Boosting, Random Forest, and Logistic Regression are analyzed [1-2].

Figure 1. The most important tasks for the further development of the digital economy in Uzbekistan.

The purpose of the study is to assess the role of these technologies in reducing financial risks, compare their accuracy and flexibility indicators, and analyze the systems, automated methods, specific features of models and statistical results operating in the world.

II. Systems for assessing the ability of individuals to pay.

1. Credit Scoring Systems: Systems such as FICO Score and VantageScore are used to analyze a person's **payment** history. They are most commonly used to assess the possibility of obtaining a loan.

FICO Score is a score based on the information in your credit report. A three - digit number based on your credit score. This helps lenders determine your likelihood of repaying a loan This, in turn, affects how much you can borrow, how many monthly payments you have to make, and how much it will cost (interest rate). FICO is an abbreviation for Fair Isaac Corporation, and is also the name of the credit scoring model developed by Fair Isaac Corporation. A FICO credit score is a tool used by many lenders to determine a person's eligibility for a credit card, mortgage, or other loan. The social categories considered are the person's payment history (35%), loan amounts (30 %), length of credit history (15 %), new credit accounts (10 %) and types of loans used (10 %). FICO scores are the most important information available on a consumer's credit report. There are three major credit bureaus in the world. 700 credit points are the most widely distributed credit points, ranging from 300 to 850.

VantageScore - Three credit reporting agencies, Experian, TransUnion and Equifax, formed a joint venture in 2006 to acquire **VantageScore**. Since then, the company has released five credit scoring models. The most widely used are VantageScore 3.0 and VantageScore 4.0.

VantageScore has announced its VantageScore 4plus model for May 2024. All three models Scores range from 300 to 850. You can see one of your VantageScore credit scores if you check your credit on a personal finance - focused website or from your credit card issuer or bank . Let 's briefly review how the models differ from each other [2-3]

VantageScore v a FICO Score

Both the VantageScore and FICO credit scores are designed to indicate the likelihood of a borrower defaulting on their financial obligations. With the exception of models that incorporate bank information, such as VantageScore 4plus and UltraFICO, credit scores are based solely on information from one of your credit reports. However, credit scores from all companies are similar and different. The three most recent VantageScore credit scores range from 300 to 850. The FICO score is typically used by all types of lenders, ranging from 300 to 850. However, the FICO score for auto lenders ranges from 250 to 900 for most credit card issuers. The two companies' credit scores look at the same type of information — the information on your credit report. However, each scoring model may look at slightly different data points and weigh the information differently.

Table 1. Characteristics of the VantageScore and FICO Score systems.

FICO rating		VantageScore 4.0	
Features	Pointer	Features	Pointer
Payment history	35%	Payment history	Very good
Loan amounts	30%	Total credit utilization	The higher the better .
Length of credit history	15%	Credit approach and experience	The higher the better .
New loan	10%	New accounts opened	Half a cup is good.

2. Banks Internal Models: All financial institutions have their own customers out of the system for special work. This is useful. For example, Chase or HSBC have internal algorithms for assessing their own credit risks. A large financial institution, such as Chase or HSBC, has its own internal credit risk algorithms and model work. These algorithms often analyze the following data:

Figure 2. Bank 's internal models

Example:

- Predicting the client 's actions

- potential default risk.

Various systems and algorithms are used around the world to determine a person's solvency. Their effectiveness and degree of widespread use are evaluated based on indicators (accuracy, degree of risk reduction, speed).

- **accuracy: Systems based on** machine learning algorithms (Zest AI, Upstart) show the best results (90–95% accuracy).
- **Scope according to:** FICO Score world like this the most wide scattered system.
- **compatibility:** Open **Banking** systems are effective because they are integrated with new technologies and real-time data [3-4].

Table 2.

The effectiveness of various systems and algorithms in determining an individual's solvency.

System	A purity (%)	Speed	Field of application	A- factors
FICO Score	80–85	High (fast)	Loans, mortgages	Reliable, universal
VantageScore	78–85	Half a year	Loans and small loans	Suitable for new customers
Machine learning systems	85–95	High	Fintech and banks	No traditional data analysis
Zest AI and Upstart	90–95	High	Digital lending	Innovation, high precision
Open Banking	85–90	High	European and Asian markets	Real - time data analysis

The choice of system depends on the needs of the organization, available data and infrastructure. Therefore, a combined approach (FICO + Machine Learning systems) is considered the most effective in most cases [4-7].

These algorithms also support AI-based learning processes, which allows them to make faster and more accurate decisions. In particular, international banks such as HSBC take into account the legislative requirements of different countries and changes in the market.

III. Formation of a data set to predict the solvency of individuals

The solvency of individuals, covers financial, demographic and behavioral characteristics. This data set is important in determining the payment discipline of loan applicants and assessing credit risk. The data set consists of three tables reflecting various indicators of applicants, each table covering specific aspects of the analysis of solvency. These indicators can be used together in the development of data analysis and predictive models, which provides a high level of accuracy and efficiency in making lending decisions [7].

Dataset structure

The dataset consists of three main tables:

- **Demographic and financial characteristics:** Includes applicants' age, source of income, monthly income, and income category.
- **Credit risk indicators:** Shows applicants' debt-to-income ratio, credit risk level, credit score, and risk category.

- **Additional financial indicators:** Includes applicants' savings, requested loan amount, and payment history (on-time payment percentage).
is linked together by applicant ID, making it easier to combine and analyze data.

Table 3. Demographic and financial characteristics

No.	Applicant ID	Age range	Source of income	Monthly income (UZS)	Category
1	Applicant_001	20-30	Salary	5,000,000	Medium
2	Applicant_002	30-40	Freelance	4,800,000	Medium
3	Applicant_003	30-40	Business	7,200,000	High
4	Applicant_004	40-50	Freelance	6,500,000	High
5	Applicant_005	20-30	Salary	4,500,000	Medium
6	Applicant_006	30-40	Business	4,200,000	Medium
7	Applicant_007	30-40	Freelance	6,000,000	High
8	Applicant_008	40-50	Business	5,800,000	High
9	Applicant_009	20-30	Salary	4,900,000	Medium
10	Applicant_010	30-40	Business	4,700,000	Medium
11	Applicant_011	30-40	Business	8,000,000	High
12	Applicant_012	40-50	Salary	7,500,000	High
13	Applicant_013	20-30	Salary	5,200,000	Medium
14	Applicant_014	30-40	Salary	5,000,000	Medium

provides basic demographic and financial information of applicants:

- **Age Range:** Applicants are divided into three age groups: 20-30, 30-40, and 40-50.
- **Source of income:** Salary, freelance or business.
- **Monthly income:** In UZS, it varies from 4,200,000 to 8,000,000.
- **Category:** Classified as “Middle” or “High” depending on income level.

Table 4. Credit risk indicators

No	Applicant ID	Age range	Debt-to-income ratio	Credit risk level	Credit rating	Risk category
1	Applicant_001	20-30	0.15	Low	720	Low risk
2	Applicant_002	30-40	0.45	High	580	High risk
3	Applicant_003	30-40	0.20	Low	700	Low risk
4	Applicant_004	40-50	0.50	High	550	High risk
5	Applicant_005	20-30	0.18	Low	710	Low risk
6	Applicant_006	30-40	0.22	Low	690	Low risk
7	Applicant_007	30-40	0.25	Low	680	Low risk
8	Applicant_008	40-50	0.23	Low	675	Low risk
9	Applicant_009	20-30	0.19	Low	705	Low risk
10	Applicant_010	30-40	0.21	Low	695	Low risk
11	Applicant_011	30-40	0.17	Low	725	Low risk
12	Applicant_012	40-50	0.20	Low	700	Low risk

13	Applicant_013	20-30	0.16	Low	730	Low risk
14	Applicant_014	30-40	0.18	Low	710	Low risk

This table contains important indicators for assessing credit risk:

- **Debt-to-income ratio:** The ratio of debt to monthly income, ranging from 0.15 to 0.50.
- **Credit risk level:** Classified as "Low" or "High".
- **Credit score:** 550 to 730, with a higher score indicating lower risk.
- **Risk category:** "Low risk" or "High risk"

Table 5. Additional financial indicators

No	Applicant ID	Age range	Fund (UZS)	Requested loan amount (UZS)	Payment history (% on time)
1	Applicant_001	20-30	2,000,000	10,000,000	95
2	Applicant_002	30-40	1,500,000	12,000,000	80
3	Applicant_003	30-40	3,000,000	15,000,000	90
4	Applicant_004	40-50	2,500,000	18,000,000	75
5	Applicant_005	20-30	1,800,000	8,000,000	92
6	Applicant_006	30-40	1,600,000	9,000,000	88
7	Applicant_007	30-40	2,200,000	12,000,000	85
8	Applicant_008	40-50	2,000,000	14,000,000	80
9	Applicant_009	20-30	1,900,000	10,000,000	90
10	Applicant_010	30-40	1,700,000	11,000,000	87
11	Applicant_011	30-40	3,500,000	16,000,000	93
12	Applicant_012	40-50	3,200,000	17,000,000	89
13	Applicant_013	20-30	2,100,000	9,000,000	94
14	Applicant_014	30-40	2,000,000	10,000,000	91

This table provides additional financial information:

- **Funding:** Applicants' funds, ranging from 1,500,000 UZS to 3,500,000 UZS.
- **Requested loan amount:** from 8,000,000 UZS to 18,000,000 UZS.
- **Payment history:** Percentage of on-time payments, ranging from 75% to 95%.

This dataset can serve as an important tool for banks or financial institutions in managing credit risk. With the right analysis and model, lending decisions become more accurate and effective [6-8].

IV. Models and algorithms for determining a person's solvency

Machine learning regression, decision tree, random forest, to determine a person's ability to pay, **Algorithms such as Gradient Boosting (XGBoost , LightGBM, CatBoost)** are considered effective. Using mathematical models to determine an individual's ability to pay helps lenders or credit institutions assess the possibility of obtaining a loan. Each model or algorithm has its own unique approach, and they are used to calculate an individual's ability to pay based on different data.

1. Logistic Regression: Logistic regression is the most widely used method in statistical modeling and is used to estimate the probability of a person's ability to repay a loan. In this model, the decision is divided into two states: pay (1) or do not pay (0).

2. Random Forest: Combines multiple decision trees and combines their results using majority voting. High accuracy, reduces the problem of overfitting. Requires computing power and memory.

3. Support Vector Machines (SVM): Creates the best separation boundary (hyperplane) for the data. Effective for working with complex and high-dimensional data. Requires a lot of computation and memory, and can be difficult with incorrect parameters.

4. Gradient Boosting (XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost) : It is considered one of the most effective machine learning methods for assessing a person's solvency. These algorithms are widely used by credit institutions, banks, and fintech companies to predict the likelihood of borrowers repaying.

5. Neural Networks: Neural networks are a multi-layered model that can be used to predict a person's ability to pay. The model consists of several layers, each layer has a neuronal layer and is connected daily. It allows for complex and deep learning from the data set. Data modeling using neural networks. High performance, deep learning through multilayer networks for large and complex data. Disadvantages: Requires a lot of data and strong computing power, complexity in application [8-9].

1. Logistic Regression a (Logistic Regression): Logistic regression an Algorithm calculates 0 and 1 or 0 and 1 for each person, y as a probability attribute. After creating the model, collecting data, parameters are optimized. This is the " maximum likelihood estimation « (MLE) method.

Output Probability: In the Logistic Regression model, the output probability for each input x is expressed as:

$$D(y=1|x)=\sigma(s)=\frac{1}{1+e^{-s}}$$

Here: $D(y=1|x)$ - this is the probability that y=1 for $\sigma(s)$ the input value . - sigmoid or logistic function.

$s=(w^T x+u)$ — is a linear combination, where: w — vector of weights, x — vector of input variables,

it is a bias or constant.

Sigmoid function: The model uses the sigmoid (logistic) function to represent the

probability. This function is expressed $\sigma(s)=\frac{1}{1+e^{-s}}$ as a function that ranges between 0 and 1, which is suitable for representing the probability.

Loss function: The Logistic Regression model learns by minimizing a loss function called binary cross-entropy or log loss. The loss function is defined as:

$$Y(f,u)=-\frac{1}{N}\sum_{i=1}^N(y_i(y_i|x_i))+(1-y_i)\log(1-D(y_i|x_i))$$

Where: N is the number of samples, y_i - the actual output value (0 or 1), $D(y_i|x_i)$ - the probabilities predicted by the Logistic Regression model.

Optimize the model using Gradient Descent:

Weight coefficients in the model \square and bias \square parameters are required to be updated, for which the gradient descent method is effective.

$$f := f - \alpha \frac{\partial Y}{\partial f}, \quad u := u - \alpha \frac{\partial Y}{\partial u}$$

Here: α is the learning rate, $\frac{\partial Y}{\partial f}$ and $\frac{\partial Y}{\partial u}$ are the gradients [9-11].

2. Random Forest: This is an ensemble learning algorithm that is widely used in classification and regression problems, providing stable and accurate results. This algorithm is composed of a large number of Decision Tree models, each tree is trained independently and their results are combined.

Random Feature Selection: At each node, only a small number of randomly selected features from all the features are considered for data partitioning. For classification problems, M features are usually selected, and for regression problems, $M/3$ features are selected. Here: M is the total number of features, and the errors are determined by Gini impurity, Entropy, or MSE from the selected features. In classification problems, Random Forest calculates the votes of all trees and selects the class with the most votes:

$$T = \arg \max_k \sum_{i=1}^B h_i(x)$$

Here: $h_i(x)$ — if the i -tree selects the \square -class for x , the value will be 1, otherwise it will be 0.

B is the number of trees. In regression problems, the average of the predictions of all trees in the Random Forest is taken:

$$T = \frac{1}{B} \sum_{i=1}^B h_i(x)$$

Here is $h_i(x)$ the prediction of the i -tree for x [10-11].

3. Support Vector Machines (SVM): The algorithm is a powerful algorithm that can be generalized to linear or nonlinear problems in classification and regression. The main task of the SVM algorithm is to find the hyperplane separating the classes and create optimal boundaries (support vectors). To find the optimal hyperplane in SVM, let's say we have two classes and for each class x_i there is $x_i \in R^2$ a feature vector and a class label. In this case: $y_i, y_i \in \{-1, +1\}$, that is, the hyperplane equation for classification into two classes $w \cdot x + u = 0$ is as follows. Here: w is the normal vector for hyperplane, u is the compensation value of hyperplane. The SVM algorithm solves the following optimization problem to find the optimal hyperplane:

$$\min_{w, u} \frac{1}{2} \|w\|^2, \quad y_i(w \cdot x_i + u) \geq 1, \quad \forall i = 1, 2, \dots, N$$

Here, $y_i(w \cdot x_i + u) \geq 1$ the equation: ensures that each point is in the correct class. As a result, once the solution is found, the hyperplane parameters are expressed as:

$$w = \sum_{i=1}^N \alpha_i \cdot y_i \cdot x_i, \quad u = y_i - w \cdot x_i$$

The general mathematical model of the SVM Algorithm $g(x) = \text{sgn}(\sum_{i=1}^N a_i y_i(x_i, x) + u)$ uses a formula for classification. The mathematical model of the SVM algorithm ends with the identification of a hyperplane that separates classes accurately and optimally [11-13].

VI. Experiment results

The dataset can be used to predict solvency using machine learning. The following features are used as input for the model:

- **Input features:** Age range, source of income, monthly income, debt-to-income ratio, savings, loan amount requested, payment history.
- **Output variable:** Risk category (Low risk or High risk) or credit rating.

Using the data, we place the dataset we need for intelligent analysis into a programming environment for analysis. Since the python programming language and its capabilities are very large for intelligent data analysis and working with machine learning algorithms, we mainly use the pandas, numpy, scikit-learn, seaborn, and matplotlib libraries of this language.

ID	Applicant ID	Age Range	Income Source	Monthly Income (UZS)	Savings (UZS)	Debt-to-Income Ratio	Requested Loan Amount (UZS)	Payment History(% on time)	Category	Credit Risk Level	Credit Score	Risk Category
1	Applicant_001	20-30	Salary	5,000,000	2,000,000	0.15	1,000,000	78	Medium	Low	720	Low Risk
2	Applicant_002	30-40	Freelance	4,800,000	1,500,000	0.45	1,200,000	80	Medium	High	580	High Risk
3	Applicant_003	30-40	Business	7,200,000	3,000,000	0.20	1,500,000	85	High	Low	458	Low Risk
4	Applicant_004	40-50	Freelance	6,500,000	2,500,000	0.50	1,400,000	75	High	High	550	High Risk
5	Applicant_005	20-30	Salary	4,500,000	1,800,000	0.18	1,650,000	87	Medium	High	670	Low Risk

Figure 3. Merging and editing a dataset using pandas.

The general initial set was created in this way, now as we can see, it is necessary to eliminate several shortcomings and prepare the set for machine learning. Since this data set is small but complex, logistic regression is the simplest and most effective algorithm is selected.

Logistic regression is a statistical and machine learning method used to solve binary classification problems, which predicts the probability of a given outcome being 0 or 1. Let's take a closer look at the data in the table. First, we can see that there are missing (NaN) values in the data, and the logistic regression algorithm is not able to handle missing values, so it is necessary to fill or remove them. In this case, for numeric variables, it is filled with the average values, and for categorical variables, it is effective to fill with the most frequently occurring value [14-15].

ID	Applicant ID	Age Range	Income Source	Monthly Income (UZS)	Savings (UZS)	Debt-to-Income Ratio	Requested Loan Amount (UZS)	Payment History(% on time)	Category	Credit Risk Level	Credit Score	Risk Category
1	Applicant_001	20-30	Salary	5,000,000	2,000,000	0.15	1,000,000	78	Medium	Low	720	Low Risk
2	Applicant_002	30-40	Freelance	4,800,000	1,500,000	0.45	1,200,000	80	Medium	High	580	High Risk
3	Applicant_003	30-40	Business	7,200,000	3,000,000	0.20	1,500,000	85	High	Low	458	Low Risk
4	Applicant_004	40-50	Freelance	6,500,000	2,500,000	0.50	1,400,000	75	High	High	550	High Risk

Figure 3. Filling NaN values in a set with average values

Since logistic regression only works with numeric variables, it is necessary to convert categorical variables to numeric. Encoding the categorical variables in the set using the LabelEncoder method gives the best results. After converting the categorical variables to numeric, the training part of the data begins.

ID	Applicant ID	Age Range	Income Source	Monthly Income (UZS)	Savings (UZS)	Debt-to-Income Ratio	Requested Loan Amount (UZS)	Payment History(% on time)	Category	Credit Risk Level	Credit Score	Risk Category
1	0	0	2	18	16	0.150000	1000000	78	0	0	720	0
2	1	10	1	13	0	0.450000	1200000	80	0	1	580	1
3	2	10	0	39	30	0.200000	1500000	85	1	0	458	0
4	3	20	1	34	26	0.500000	1400000	75	1	1	550	1
5	4	0	2	4	8	0.180000	1650000	87	0	1	670	0

Figure 4. Coding categorical variables in a set to convert them to numeric representation.

For logistic regression, we need to split the data set into characteristics and a target variable. In this case, we take the column named “Risk Category” as the target variable, and as characteristics, usually another column or all columns are used, we use all the remaining columns.

The data into train and test sets for training and perform initial training to check the accuracy of the model. The evaluation methods in the logistic regression algorithm are *Accuracy*, *precision*, *recall* and *f1-score*. Classification metrics are used and help analyze the results of the model from different perspectives.

Table 6. Initial prediction results of the logistic regression model

Logistic regression algorithm	Evaluation methods			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
	50%	83%	56%	67%

Logistics regression in algorithms *accuracy* indicator more accuracy criterion as used and we have this is 50% organization This is indicator increase for below from methods one *standardization* done increasing We 'll see .

To get a good result in logistic regression, we perform a standardization procedure. Logistic regression focuses heavily on differences between variables, so the data needs to be normalized or standardized. To do this, we use Python's *StandardScaler* function to standardize the data, i.e., to bring it to the range [0,1], and then train our previous model on the standardized data set again to get the results.

Table 7. Model prediction results after data standardization

Logistic regression algorithm	Evaluation methods			
	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
	70%	100%	67%	80%

The model results increased significantly after standardization. Therefore, it can be seen how important the preparation of data for machine learning algorithms is. To improve the performance of the model, it is first necessary to prepare the existing data set in its complete form, not in its raw form. To increase the accuracy of the model, it is recommended to increase the missing features, use optimization methods, and adjust hyperparameters [16-18].

VII. Conclusion:

Determining the solvency of individuals is of strategic importance in modern financial systems and plays a key role in automating lending, risk management, and decision-making processes. This study comprehensively analyzes the application of artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms in assessing the solvency of individuals, and explores their scientific and practical significance. The study discusses machine learning algorithms such as

Gradient Boosting (XGBoost, LightGBM, CatBoost), Random Forest, Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machines (SVM), and neural networks, along with traditional credit scoring systems such as FICO Score and VantageScore. The mathematical models of each algorithm, including components such as loss functions, gradient computations, random feature selection, and hyperplane optimization, are covered in detail.

Machine learning algorithms include the need for large computational resources, dependence on data quality, and reduced efficiency due to incorrect parameter settings. In the future, the development of artificial intelligence, machine learning, and blockchain technologies will increase transparency, security, and efficiency in financial systems. At the same time, special attention should be paid to data privacy, information security, and ethical issues. In conclusion, artificial intelligence and machine learning algorithms offer significant opportunities in reducing financial risks, improving decision-making, and developing the digital economy.

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